

The Practice of Mindfulness in the Classroom its impact on students' Academic performance: A Review Based on available literature

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ABSTRACT

The present system of teaching learning is not effective enough to make student focus and have maximum attention in the class room during teaching learning process which has a risk of losing the significance of structured or formal education. Mindfulness or meditation in the classroom has significant effects and benefits for students. This paper aims to identify the benefits of mindfulness and its practice in class room among students in their education and academic performance.

INTRODUCTION

Education in the present scenario has a dynamic effect on all the aspects of cognitive, conative, and affective by the tools and teaching methods. Similarly in education, various methods are used in the teaching-learning process. A study conducted by The National Commission for Protection of Child Rights (NCPCR) states that due to smart phone usage 37.15% children's go through low levels of concentration always or frequently¹. Mindfulness or meditation in the classroom has significant effects and benefits on the academic and clinical performance of students. The mental state achieved by meditation allows the individual to become fully aware of the internal and external events existing in the present moment². Meditation also improves and helps in maintaining attention, self-regulation³ academic performance, management of academic-related stress⁴ and other benefits of meditation includes memory, stress management, overcoming anxiety.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK IMPORTANCE IN EDUCATION

Learning in structured educational environment the college or educational institute contributes to effective development of competency which includes knowledge and skill of specific discipline further its unique to self and the society. Every student spending the quality time being in the learning environment should result in learning for which attention, free from anxiety, focus, concentration, memory, intelligence has greater importance which are achievable through mindfulness or meditation practice as a part of education programme.

METHODS

Search Strategy methods an electronic search of articles published in various journals from 2014 to 2023 was conducted. The search was restricted to only English language. The database search done was Pubmed-Medline and CINAHL, EBESCO, Science direct, Google scholar, Research Gate. Articles containing following key search terms were retrieved.

Types of Interventions:

1. Practice
2. Training
3. Mindfulness
4. Meditation

Types of Research Studies:

Randomized controlled trials, pre-experimental, qualitative studies, Factorial designs, cross-sectional studies.

Type of Participants:

Students of Higher education, School students, University students, Nursing students.

Settings:

1. Academic Institution
2. University.

Outcomes

Improving academic performance, attention, focus, and relief from anxiety in the classroom through mindfulness.

RESULTS

The systematic search was conducted by framing the terms individually and in combination with all keywords and synonyms, also according to the database. In addition to this, a manual PUBMED, EBSCO AND GOOGLE SCHOLER, RESEARCH GATE search was undertaken using the keywords and search synonyms from already found articles. Initial search retrieved 1033 articles selected manually. Duplication was removed and reviewed 130 articles for eligibility. 624 articles were excluded because of duplications further 116 more studies were excluded due to the unavailability of the full text. Hence 10 articles were screened finally.

3.1. PRISMA CHART

Figure 2. Flow chart showing the study selection process

Table 1. Data Extraction Table

S.N & authors name/study year	Research design	Findings & conclusion of the study
1. Lorenza Corti, Carmen Gelati (2020)	Pre-experimental	A study on mindfulness and coaching to improve learning abilities in university students. The results revealed that the students improved in self-awareness, the ability of self-evaluation, the skills of metacognition & organization, to manage study materials, and their own intelligence confidence and suggested coaching a mindfulness as a short time intervention can improve students' effective learning ⁵ .
2. Paulina Ziolkowska (2020)	Cross-sectional design	The Effects of Meditation on College Students in Relation to Academic Performance and Satisfaction of Participation in Higher level Education. The results demonstrated that regular meditation is significantly associated with higher academic performance, and higher level of satisfaction of participation in higher level education. The regular meditative group scored significantly higher than the non-meditative group on all presented measures. These findings suggest that by engaging in regular meditation college students may significantly improve their academic performance, and that as regular meditation may be a practical technique for college students to improve academically ⁴ .
3. Runnan Zhang (2019)	2X2 factorial design	A study on the effect of meditation on concentration level and cognitive performance. The study did not find evidence of improvement of test performance by meditation and suggested that the concentration level has improved as per the participants feedback obtained subjectively ⁶ .
4. Michael F. S. Baranski, Christopher A. Was (2019)	Randomized Control Design	A study on can mindfulness meditation Improve Short-term and Long-term Academic Achievement in a Higher-education Course? The results revealed that on academic achievement the effects were not evident but because of inconsistent effects, the researchers work should explore future studies of mindfulness meditation based on the differences in individuals, duration, number of times, and type of meditation practice and its benefits ⁷ .

5. Lin, Jian Wei; Mai, Li Jung (2020)	Randomized Control Design	Impact of Mindfulness Meditation Intervention on Academic Performance. The study findings revealed that the experimental group had better short-term academic performance but similar
		long-term academic performance. Within the experimental group, students with high meditation depth achieved better short-term academic performance than those with low meditation depth. Finally, the questionnaire results revealed that most students enjoyed the MM process and agreed that the intervention improves in-class learning efficiency ⁸ .
6. Destany Calma-Birling, Regan A.R. Gurung (2017)	Randomized Control Design	A study on does a brief mindfulness intervention impact quiz performance? The results revealed that small doses of mindfulness training for students can enhance knowledge retention relatedto content of lecture.
7. Kathleen G. Burger, Joan Such Lockhart, (2017)	Randomized-control trial	Meditation's Effect on Attentional Efficiency, Stress, and Mindfulness Characteristics of Nursing Students. Thesults revealed that Meditation demonstrated moderate strength for enhancing executive attention, $F = 4.26 (1, 49), n^2 = .080, p = .044$. Additional outcomes specific to the meditation group were reduced stress and increased mindfulness, $F = 7.16 (2, 47), n^2 = .234, p = .002$ & concluded that the consideration of meditation training as a strategy for enhancing nursing students' attentional efficiency and other self-regulatory skills necessary for safe nursing practice.

<p>8. Jasna K. Schwind a, *, Elizabeth McCay A, Heather Beanlands et. Al (2017)</p>	<p>Qualitative exploratory pilot study</p>	<p>Mindfulness practice as a teaching-learning strategy in higher education: A qualitative exploratory pilot study. Students reported an increased sense of calm, and a decreased feeling of anxiety. Lovingkindness meditation was mostly perceived as a positive way to close the class. Their instructors also observed that the brief mindful breathing practice at start of class helped students become more grounded and focused before engaging in the course content. Challenges encountered focused on the need to provide more in-depth information about mindfulness, as it relates to higher education teaching-learning contexts, to both students and participating instructors. Conclusions: Implications for education suggest further research that includes fuller experiential training of participating instructors, as well as provision of a more comprehensive background on mindfulness to students.</p>
<p>9. Pamela van der Riet , Rachel</p>	<p>Descriptive qualitative design</p>	<p>Piloting a stress management and mindfulness program for undergraduate nursing students: student feedback and lessons learned. The findings</p>
<p>Rossiter , Dianne Kirby (2015)</p>		<p>revealed that positive impact concentration, clarity of thought and a reduction in negative cognitions. Overall, this pilot program enhanced the participants' sense of well-being. Despite the challenges, benefits were identified on a personal and professional level¹⁰.</p>
<p>10. Tang YY, Tang R, Jiang C, Posner MI (2014)</p>	<p>Randomized-control trial</p>	<p>Short-Term Meditation Intervention Improves Self-Regulation and Academic Performance. The results revealed that with 10 hours of IBMT significantly improved both executive and alerting attention (P <0.01), indicating the greater self-control and sustained attention ability. We also tested whether intelligence improved aier training. Paired t tests before and aier training showed a sLJnLčcant improvement in Raven scores (P <0.001). Concluded that brief mindfulness meditation is an effective intervention for improving attention, emotion and academic performance¹¹.</p>

SUMMARY OF FINDING:

The literature available has the following findings:

- Mindfulness practice in classroom can reduce stress, anxiety and promotes sustained attention and focus, self-awareness in class room, concentration and memory.
- It also contributes to high academic performance as well as improvement of intelligence and decision making.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In the current scenario the availability, and accessibility of resources entertainment through digital media has impacted the attention span and concentration reducing it considerably among students in class room which further has negative impact on learning and education, to prevent further damage and overcome these effects mindfulness practice will be an effective measure and so it should be considered as one of the options to be used by all academicians, instructors and teachers to put it in to practice and further research can be done to identify specific methods of meditation that can contribute.

FURTHER STUDY

With research limited to variables, researchers recommend that similar research be conducted targeting different generations different groups or variables. As a result, adding mediating variables can it can also be studied by future researchers to gain new insight into this matter relationship between variables. To determine if any are significant. Apart from that, the results of this research can help future researchers identify what improvements can be made to be more sustainable and able to deal with change preferences and needs. Recommendations above will help researchers to identify what factors have a significant influence purchasing behavior of different generations comes from different cultures background.

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